

BOOST Project: D4.1 Working Group, Workshops, User Surveys and Key Reports

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Introduction

NERC has managed data access and sharing policies since its creation in 1965. Today, the Environmental Data Service (EDS)¹ provides integrated data services across its five data centres, including operational analysis platforms, across all NERC² domains. Most science applications are becoming increasingly multidisciplinary; The EDS is working towards providing environmental data users with a “one stop shop” for data services. The EDS forms part of NERC’s digital strategy and implementation, working across discipline boundaries to break down barriers and facilitate data sharing.

The EDS, with partners, will pilot cloud native FAIR data services to support cross-disciplinary, pan-UKRI applications which increasingly need to combine diverse data and knowledge of the underpinning measurement and data capabilities. These services will extend our DRI Phase 1b developments of core NERC data services, building on international standards and data commons principles to link to existing cross-council DRI developments. The BOOST project has addressed :

- Data findability and traceability through Persistent Identifier registration and asset cataloguing with a novel linking of provenance via semantic graphing techniques.
- Extend data accessibility and interoperability by continuing to develop a federated Trusted Research Environment on JASMIN, ensuring compliance with DARE UK standards.
- By building on the EDS DataLabs data processing environment, create workflow services to process, quality assure and integrate large-scale genomics data that describe biodiversity.
- Enhance interoperability across disciplines by performing a detailed review of analysis platforms across disciplines and user applications, leading to recommendations for FAIR implementation.
- Support all of the above through a coordinated framework of co-creation of services and associated training with users.

¹ <https://eds.ukri.org/environmental-data-service>

² <https://www.ukri.org/councils/nerc/>

This document is concerned with activities on Work Package 4 which performed a review of Analysis Platforms with Recommendations for Interoperation. NERC and UKRI have many data analysis platforms designed to accommodate individual communities, workflows and available resources. We will exploit the RDA³ framework, emerging global trans-disciplinary standards and also develop links with CEOS⁴ and other trailblazing community groups to establish best practice. The recommendations will inform FAIR data services working within a CARE compliant framework⁵.

Workpack 4 Deliverables:

- BOOST D4.1: Working Group, Workshops, User Survey and Key Reports (**This Document**)
- BOOST D4.2: Progress with establishing a TRE on JASMIN and utilising workflows - May 9th Workshop
- BOOST D4.3: CEOS Jupyter Notebooks Best Practice V1.1
- BOOST D4.4: NERC DataLabs Fair Interoperability
- BOOST D4.5: Inter-platform/archive workflows and use cases for RO-Crates
- BOOST 4.6: Recommendation for improving the interoperability of Data Analysis Platforms

In this document BOOST D4.1 we detail the formation of the DAPI working Group, Workshops, User Survey and Key Reports.

Interoperability of Data Analysis Platforms (DAPI) Working Group

The working group was formed in March 2024 and consisted of a mix of EDS data centre representatives and UKRI data analysis platform representatives. The main aim of DAPI was to promote dialogue between the two and serve as a central forum for Work Package 4 activities. The main emphasis was on the interoperability of platforms, future plans and the scrutiny of evidence from supporting meetings and case studies.

Where relevant we aimed to identify good practice coming from, and make recommendations based on input and agreement with Data Analysis platform representatives. Our role is to facilitate the conversations, record their outcomes and present to the broader community, identifying gaps and areas for future work.

³ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/>

⁴ <https://ceos.org/>

⁵ https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5d3799de845604000199cd24/t/6397b363b502ff481fce6baf/1670886246948/CARE%2BPrinciples_One%2BPagers%2BFINAL_Oct_17_2019.pdf

Key Central and Supporting Meetings

March 18th 2024: Working group meeting 1- Covering RDA framework, FAIR and Care Principles and Topic Straw Man questions in Annex A to inform case studies and prioritise areas of investigation.

June 6th 2024: BOOST DINI meeting - Discussion on how two projects could support each other through information sharing.

July - August 2024: 1-2-1 Topic specific meetings covering Workflows, AI, Data Transfer

Sept 5th 2024: Working Group meeting 2, Platform presentations and scope review

Oct 4th 2024: WP2 and WP4 with JASMIN BGS and Digital Solutions to discuss TREs

Oct 9th 2024: Meeting with DAFNI and Charlotte Pascoe (IPCC and NERC model metadata projects) to discuss issues around implementing complex models across platforms

Oct 10th 2024: Working Group meeting 3 - Platform presentations and discussion on user survey Annex B

Oct 15th -17th 2024: CEOS WGISS 58 for D4.3 Jupyter Notebooks Best Practice case study

Oct 16th 2024: User Survey Design meeting

Oct 22nd 2024: BOOST WP4 Earth Observation Data Hub meeting on workflow technologies to feed other platforms

Oct 24th 2024: BOOST WP4 DARE UK meeting on TREs, workflows and joint workshop

Oct 25th 2024: DSIT workshop

Nov 2024: Promotion of survey, analysis and follow up interviews

Nov 13th 2024: Data Sharing Working Group with Focus on AI and Vocabularies

Dec 18th 2024: Working Group meeting 4 - Platform presentations, Review User survey results, D3.4 Jupyter notebooks best practice and recommendations

Jan 14th: Data Sharing webinar from Digital Twin Hub

Jan 31st 2025: Advancing Researcher Data Access Pilots: A Show-and-Tell Webinar

Feb 2025: 1-2-1 meetings with EDS centres to finalize recommendation and gather feedback on D4.3 using questionnaire in Annex C.

Feb 26th 2025: BOOST representative attend the Earth Observation Data Hub webinar

Mar 12th 2025: BOOST representatives attend DAFNI workshop with side meeting on recommendations and vocabularies with the Energy Data centre

Mar 26th 2025: CEOS WGISS 59

Mar 27th 2025: DSIT workshop

Current Members

DAPI member	Platform/Data Centre
Esther Conway	Centre for Environmental Data Analysis
Helen Glaves	National Geoscience Data Centre
Sam Pepler	Centre for Environmental Data Analysis
Thomas Zwagerman	UK Polar Data Centre
Helen Peat	UK Polar Data Centre
Andrew Kingdon	National Geoscience Data Centre
Gordon Blair	UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology
Helen Snaith	British Oceanographic Data Centre
Monica Hanley	British Oceanographic Data Centre
Thomas Gardner	British Oceanographic Data Centre
Adrain Hines	JASMIN
Brian Matthews	DAFNI
Helen Snaith	British Oceanographic Data Centre
Tom Kirkham	DAFNI
Federica Moscato	Earth Observation Data Hub
Robin Long	UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology
Colin Sauze	National Oceanography Centre

Potential Members and Evolution of the DAPI WG

Through working group conversations we identified a number of other platforms we would like to engage with and have initiated conversations. The Polar Data Centre have reached out to Polar Digital Twin⁶ and we also initiated conversation with CReDo⁷ via the Energy Systems Catapult⁸. We consider the inclusion of universities and key government departments as a vital part of the evolution of the working group. We continue discussion of this in D4.6 recommendations.

⁶ <https://www.bas.ac.uk/project/digital-twins-of-the-polar-regions/>

⁷ <https://digitaltwinhub.co.uk/climate-resilience-demonstrator-credo/>

⁸ <https://es.catapult.org.uk/>

Workshops

Jupyter Notebooks as a Centralised Resource Workshop at CEOS

WGISS⁹ (the Working Group on Information Systems and Services) is a working group of CEOS. WGISS promotes collaboration in the development of systems and services that manage and supply these observation data. WGISS creates and demonstrates prototypes supporting CEOS and Group on Earth Observation (GEO) requirements. WGISS also addresses the internal management of EO data, the creation of information systems and the delivery of interoperable services. The activities and expertise of WGISS span the full range of the information life cycle, from the requirements and metadata definition for the initial ingestion of satellite data into archives through to the incorporation of derived information into end-user applications.

The WGISS working group already had a technology exploration topic on Jupyter Notebooks led by Esther Conway of CEDA. It already had and established use cases, surveys and awareness raising webinars. The group had expressed a strong need for a Jupyter notebooks best practice and produced an initial list of areas to be explored. We were able to use BOOST project funding to organise a Jupyter Notebooks as a Centralised Resource Workshop at CEOS¹⁰.

Attendees at CEOS WGISS 56

⁹ <https://ceos.org/ourwork/workinggroups/wgiss/>

¹⁰ <https://ceos.org/meetings/wgiss-56/>

Registered Attendees included

Agency/Institution	Name of Attendee
Agencia Espacial Mexicana	Adrian Guzman*
CASAIR	Ziyang Li, Xuesong Li
CNES	Richard Moreno, Pierre-Marie Brunet*, Helene de Boissezon*, Guillaume Eynard-Bontemps*, Hugo Fournier, Aurélien Sacotte*
CONAE	Homero Lozza*
CSA	Joey Martin*
CSIRO	Matt Paget, Edward King*
DLR	Katrin Molch, Jonas Eberle, Felix Feckler
EC	Daniel Quintart*
ESA	Mirko Albani, Marie-Claire Greening (CEOS Executive Officer), Roberto Alacevich*, Yves Coene (Spacebel), Damiano Guerrucci, Daniele Iozzino (Rhea)*, Iolanda Maggio (Rhea), Simone Mantovani (MEEO)*, Filippo Marchesi (Solenix), Mattias Mohr*, Paulo Sacramento*, Mattia Stipa*, Marin Tudoroiu*
EUMETSAT	Daniel Lee*, Ben Loveday*, Julia Wagemann*
GA	Simon Oliver
GEO	Paola de Salvo*, Felipe Carlos*, Kalamkas Yessimkhanova
ISO TC 211	Liping Di*
ISRO	Nitant Dube, Sai Kalpana Tanguturu*

LSI-VC	Matt Steventon*
JAXA	Makoto Natsuisaka (WGISS Chair)*, Yousuke Ikehata, Michelle Piepgrass (WGISS secretary)
NASA	Dana Ostrenga*, David Borges (SEO)*, Andrew Cherry*, Valerie Dixon*, Thomas Huang*, Dawn Lowe*, Michael Morahan, Doug Newman, Patrick Quinn*, Kenton Ross*, Brian Terry(SEO)*, Min Wong*
NOAA	Kenneth (Ken) Casey*, Tyler Christensen, Nancy Ritchey*, Kathryn Shontz*
SANSA	Lisa Maria Rebelo*
UNOOSA	Jorge del Rio Vera*
UKSA	Esther Conway, Simon Clewley*, David Moffat*, Uzma Saeed (NCEO)*, Ed Williamson (STFC/CEDA)*
USGS	Thomas (Tom) Sohre (WGISS Vice-chair), Steve Labahn*. Ryan Longhenry*, Tim Mentele*, Stephen Zahn*
VSNC	Nguyen Tuencong*
WMO	Enrico Fucile*
Other	Dmitriy Utva (Dragonfly Aerospace)*, Oacar Danuek Bektrab (IDEAM)*, Alastair McKinstry (Irish Centre for High-End Computing)*, Peter Cornillon (University of Rhode Island), Stefan Wunderlee (UniBern)*, Libby Rose (Symbios)*, Kévin Gross (Visioterra)*, Grégory Mazabraud (VisioTerra)*, Jed Sundwall (Radiant)*

Presentations at the workshop

Presentation Title	Name and Institution of presenter
Working Group on Capacity Building and Data Democracy (WGCapD)	Jorge del Rio Rivera (UN)*
GEO Report	Paola de Salvo (GEO-SEC)*
Jupyter Notebooks Best Practice	Esther Conway (UKSA/CEDA)
Vision for FEDEO and ESA Registry Tools, Service Metadata and Discovery Best Practices	Yves Coene (Spacebel for ESA), Damiano Guerrucci (ESA)
Discussion, Best Practice Documents	All
Jupyter Hub, Binder and Collaboration Examples	Esther Conway (UKSA/CEDA)
CEOS Interoperability Lab (CAL)	David Borges (NASA)*
MAGEO and AI Training Notebooks	Dan Clewley (PML/NEODAAS)*
EUMETSAT Training Needs	Ben Loveday (EUMETSAT)*
NASA Development: Current Situation and Training Needs	Lauren Childs-Gleason (NASA)*, Kent Ross (NASA)*
NCEO: Current Situation and Training Needs	Uzma Zaaed (NCEO)*

The workshop held at CNES ¹¹Paris examined active Group on Earth Observation (GEO¹²) and CEOS projects and the training needs of CEOS Agencies.

Paula De Salvo presented the GEO Knowledge Hub¹³ archiving Jupyter notebooks for GEO and CEOS projects. Yves Coen and Damiano Guerci presented their vision for FEDEO¹⁴, ESA registry of tools and the service metadata and discovery best practice, thereby providing valuable insight into how these standards could effectively be used to support the longer term use of Jupyter notebooks. Esther Conway then went on to present the challenges faced by a data archive attempting to archive notebooks born on different platforms within a centralised data archive. David Borges then described the use and challenges of using Jupyter Notebooks within the CEOS Analytics Lab¹⁵.

Jupyter Notebooks were explored from a training needs perspective, as supporting training by using notebooks as a centralised training resource was thought to be an area of great potential. Dan Clewley presented the use of AI training notebooks within the MAGEO ¹⁶Jupyter hub based platform. This was followed by Ben Loveday, who gave the perspective of EUMETSAT's training hub which is one of the most developed Jupyter notebooks-based training portals. Lauren Childs-Gleason and Kenton Ross provided valuable insight into the potential of Jupyter notebooks from the capacity development perspective, detailing their current situation and training needs. The presentation concluded with Uzma Saeed describing the training needs of NCEO¹⁷ and organisations trying to support the use of EO data on a national level.

We then continued to work on the Best Practice document for the next year and published a fully endorsed version in January 2025. This has been delivered to this project as D4.3 CEOS Jupyter Notebooks Best Practice V1.1¹⁸. We then continued by doing a cross domain analysis of EDS centres based on questions in Annex C. This work was presented at CEOS WGISS-58¹⁹ where BOOST DSIT funding to support this effort was fully and properly acknowledged.

¹¹ <https://cnes.fr/en>

¹² <https://earthobservations.org/>

¹³ <https://gkhub.earthobservations.org/>

¹⁴ <https://ceos.org/ourwork/workinggroups/wgiss/access/fedeo/>

¹⁵ <https://ceos.org/cal/>

¹⁶ <https://mageohub.neodaas.ac.uk/hub/login?next=%2Fhub%2F>

¹⁷ <https://www.google.com/search?client=firefox-b-d&channel=entpr&q=NCEO>

¹⁸ https://ceos.org/document_management/Working_Groups/WGISS/Documents/WGISS%20Best%20Practices/CEOS_JupyterNotebooks_Best%20Practice_v1.1.pdf

¹⁹ <https://ceos.org/meetings/wgcv-54-wgiss-58/>

Phd Student Workshop - Session on the Data Landscape

The next workshop was the NCEO PhD training workshop held at the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory on Wednesday 13th December 2023. We presented the data and infrastructure ecosystem for Earth Observation on a number of levels. We tested the group's awareness and training needs at each level.

Navigating the Data Landscape

1. Within NCEO

CEDA, JASMIN, NEODASS, MAGEO

2. Within NERC and UK

Environmental Data Service, Institutional and Specialist Repositories

3. Within Europe

Copernicus Services, Copernicus DIAS, ESA repositories, Sentinel Hub, ESA PGDS, EUMETSAT, Zenodo, FEDEO and CEOS

4. Further Afield and Commercial

CEOS IDN, NASA, NOAA, USGS, Digital Earth Africa, Google Earth Engine, Amazon Web Services, Earthbox, Colabs and Binder

5. Next Generation UK

Jupyter, EO Data Hub, DSIT EDS Research Data Cloud Pilot project

University	No of PhD Students
University of Reading	8
University of Leicester	2
Imperial College London	2
King's College London	2
University College London	1
University of Edinburgh	1

The key finding from the workshop was that awareness of data sources with the exception of CEDA, JASMIN and Google Earth was very low. They would like more training on the digital landscape and thought this type of training should ideally begin at undergraduate level.

Joint Dare UK/BOOST Planned Workshop (Planned)

We felt it was important for the Environmental Data Service centres, scientific community and other members of the Data Analysis Platform working group to continue discussions on how we can improve the interoperability of our data and platforms. We had initially planned to hold the workshop on the 20th March 2025 however due many projects closing at the end of March we decided to reschedule to the 9th May 2025.

The aims of the workshop are as follows:

1. To gain a better understanding of what health researcher need in terms of environmental data
2. To gain a better understanding of the capacity of Health TREs
 - a. Volumes of environmental data they can accommodate
 - b. Data transfer rates that can be handled
 - c. Tools/software used by and flexibility to install new tools/software on Health TREs
3. Discuss how EDS and other data centre can promote their data holdings to health researchers
4. Discuss what sort of workflows TREs might benefit from, and the kinds of data transformation that health researchers might benefit from: for example rescaling, format conversions and compression
5. Dare UK to inform attendees on the DARE UK Federated Architecture Blueprint, vision for a “National Data Library” and inform us of relevant projects that the NERC community can engage with

BOOST User Survey

The purpose of this survey is to:

- Identify platforms that you are currently using to analyse and produce new datasets
- Understand issues/barriers that you are facing using data from different domains
- Understand barriers to using different platforms
- Understand the type and range of analysis you wish to perform

A full list of questions can be found in Annex A. We had a total of 33 respondents to surveys sent out. Below is a table giving institutions and the types of data in use. Due to GDPR, access in full is only available to DSIT/UKRI staff by request to esther.conway@stfc.ac.uk.

Institution	Data Type
Centre for Environmental Data Analysis, STFC	ESA CCI climate datasets UK Met Office operational data streams IPCC Sixth Assessment Report CMIP6 model output
Met Office	NetCDF, BADC-CSV, binary & proprietary files, ingest of large volume earth observation & atmospheric data. CMIP6 climate data, netCDF, up to 1 PB
University of Exeter	I use Jupyter notebooks for data manipulation, usually data I upload to my folder through the Jupyter notebooks interface. I work with csv and nc files. However, due to recent project work I will need to manipulate esacci data, stored in CEDA, and I would like to access that data directly from CEDA repository, without having to download it to my PC first and then uploaded to my JASMIN account space.
Polar Data Centre - NERC/UKRI	Physical science datasets / ASCII, CSV, netCDF, CDF, JSON and proprietary / kB to TB
Met Office Hadley Centre	Model Data
King's college London	ERA5, nc, 2mb each
University of Reading	Multiple file formats, including .nc, .pp (Met Office format), .csv, .hdf.

University of Sheffield	Earth System Model output (e.g. CESM2) and gridded Earth observations (e.g. HadCRUT). Usually in netCDF file format, with file sizes ranging from a few MB to hundreds of GB depending on scale/resolution.
NCAS, University of Leeds	Atmospheric datasets, such as ERA5, aircraft datasets, GOES satellite
The Amazonas State University	I use data from Climate Modelling Simulation in NetCDF format (CIDAR project)
Uni. Leicester	MOD/MYD 04 and 06 in HDF4; CCI aerosol in NCDF; ERA5 in NCDF
University of Edinburgh	Generic open source datasets for machine learning. Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2. Sizes vary but I tend to work with moderate sized datasets (e.g. 50GB)
University of Manchester	CHESS-MET (NetCDF, about 40 GB total for the variables I needed), CHESS-SCAPE (NetCDF, 86 GB), and from other sources: ESDAC (soil hydraulic properties) and SoilGrids (soil texture properties).
NCEO - University of Leicester	JULES model data, satellite data (e.g. LST, soil moisture, FAPAR, methane, etc.)
Retired	Rainfall climate
University of Manchester	Atmospheric data: aircraft data FAAM (aerosol, trace gas, cloud microphysics and lidar); IAGOS data (long term airborne water vapour, trace gas CO, NO _x , N ₂ O, O ₃ , CH ₄ , CO ₂ , aerosol and cloud-dust concentrations); UK monitoring station data incl. trace gas, aerosol PM and aerosol composition data (e.g. MERI AMS, SP2) and integrated meteorological data (pressure, temperature RH, solar radiation, UV, precipitation); land use data (UK CEH); Real-time spectated pollen and fungal spore data (MERI-Swisens Jupiter, soon B'ham - more sites required however to deliver meaningful research deliverables)
University of Leicester	Level 1 IR data from Sentinel 3, MODIS; ECMWF-ERA5 analysis and forecast. In netCDF format where available
NCAS	Weather surveillance radar (WSR) data - typically

	netcdf. Associated surface observations, often csv.
University of Exeter	PAMIP contribution to CMIP6, netCDF, TBs.
University of Huddersfield	River level data
Government	Monthly temperature and wind speed data
None	Midas
Manchester Metropolitan University	Mostly meteorological data such as UKMO data, ECMWF, CMIP, etc.
Cranfield University	MIDAS open data
University of Reading	NetCDF files from CMIP and other MIPs, some of which are stored in /badc/ and others in GWSs. Pretty big files! Don't know the exact numbers but I've used TBs of data.
RSPB	Sentinel 1, Sentinel 2. File formats .jpg2000, .GTiff, .GRD
NCAS & University of Cambridge	UKESM model output from various simulations run on Monsoon and ARCHER. CMIP6 and CCM1 data produced from UKESM and other models. Observational data from FAAM and other aircraft, and satellite products.
Agri-Food and Biosciences Institute AFBI	Rainfall and weather data (CEDA archive - MIDAS stations); 1m LiDAR DTM at national scales (LAS, TIF, GB sizes); nutrient time series from river monitoring , soil data (SNHS) (our own data)
University of Reading	Data from weather and climate simulations and meteorological observations from a variety of instruments (mostly based at the Chilbolton Atmospheric Observatory)
University College London	Met Office Nimrod data esp. radar, MSG satellite imagery
None	AI and Data Research. Far too many sets to describe here and also commercially sensitive.
Cefas	Ocean data
University of Birmingham	Energy data from various sources. Including Elexon, Electrification of Heat demonstration project (>2GB many csv files), RHPP data (similar to EoH), Low carbon London (hundreds of MB), weather data (a few MBs)

We acknowledge the limitations of the survey as it went out on JASMIN, CEDA, BODC and PDC websites and mailing lists. However, this does limit feedback to established EDS service users. There is a need to target users from a greater range of domain and user type. As stated above, we would need to evolve the working group to engage with a broader audience. We also believe that our data is underexploited and has the potential to be used by more discipline and user types.

Key outcomes

Sources of Environmental Data

There is strong evidence of our communities using data from multiple sources with some cross domain mainly from the environmental domain but some cross domain use in evidence. International and commercial providers are in evidence. When sensitive data is mentioned, users describe use of UKRI for processing then transfer to a more secure environment to combine with sensitive data.

Data interoperability issues cited by users

We asked our users about difficulties:

1. Formats and compliance with standard formats is one of the biggest issues cited by users

“Format difficult to uses and non compliance with formats an issues”

“File formats are always an issue, with UKESM output being in pp format and others in NetCDF. sometimes the datasets are large and difficult and slow to process. Accessing observational products can be tricky due to the file format, metadata, and especially changing variable names.”

2. Semantics is another big concern for our users

“Semantics is always an issue “

“Main difficulty is semantics many domains do not have an agreed set of terms or dictionaries/ontologies to enable true interoperability”

3. Coping with volume, structure, scale or projection

The main issues faced by our user are dealing with volumes, rescaling, reprojecting, restructuring, extracting/subsetting and aggregation. It is important that in follow up interviews there were also comments on how action such as rescaling EO data can drastically affect uncertainties and any workflows that enable these kinds of action need to be accompanied by appropriate levels of uncertainty information.

“Combining data of different scales or different projection”

“Data Volume and size - extracting the data you want”

“Aggregation and creating time series data”

What platforms are being used ?

We can see from this small sample the range of platforms, personal PCs, university HPC, UKRI data platforms and commercial services that our users are employing

JASMIN, Windows PC's, Linux workstations, UEA HPC, Google Colabs, Leicester HPC, Orchid GPU cluster on JASMIN, ARC4 University of Leeds, Reading Academic Compute Cluster (RACC), Monsoon (Met Office), Local Linux system, laptop, AWS Cloud, UK Met. Office for certain collaborative projects, Google Earth code editor

We also have users that create their own bespoke environments:

“We have our own bespoke AI driven analytics platforms that outputs data to any desired target format”.

What activities are being carried out on the different platforms?

The survey yielded many examples of how activities can be used on multiple platforms which are useful for different things. This can be for heavy processing, numbers of users that can be supported, stability of service, flexibility of environments, security/sensitivity of data, data sharing and training.

“yes I process on Jasmin and visualize on my own PC”

“I combine Met Office internal HPC and JASMIN. I primarily use Met Office facilities and then jump to JASMIN when I need to share data.”

“Develop , generally in Python IDE (Pycharm) within a container on laptop then move to other system be it internal Linux system the UK Met. Office or AWS cloud for example”

“I use Monsoon to run the Unified Model, and either archive to MASS or rsync direct transfer data to JASMIN. I use Globus/wget/requests to retrieve data from other sources. I use JASMIN notebooks to share/expose data to other JASMIN users.”

“Generally I perform modelling experiments on HPCs (mainly ARCHER2, but also Derecho in the US) and transfer subsets of the output to JASMIN for analysis.”

“It's very cumbersome download then tensorflow” (on personal platform)

“I collect and archive data on CEDA and local databases and use spatial data to place aircraft and local surface data in context for model studies, some of which use new AI tools to determine meteorological and trace gas driver impacts on specific aerosol (bio) emissions.”

“Yes I use Google colab and lightning AI to train CNN/ DNN models and predict to areas of interest. I then download the predictions to manipulate and evaluate these on my own PC.”

“I primarily use JASMIN, and occasionally the local servers for smaller amounts of analysis when JASMIN is having issues. For training purposes I use AWS EC2 instances and provide a sub-set of data there for students to use. Python notebooks are stored on GitHub.”

“Numerous platforms are used, details are commercially sensitive.”

“I use github to share jupyter notebooks, more recently colab to publish alongside papers.”

Is there anything that would improve interoperability ?

“I would like there to be a standardised method of programmatically accessing data in a straightforward manner, to save time finding the best way of downloading data from each source in this ecosystem.”

“We have models on our existing university infrastructure and on JASMIN. Would be useful if we can process the data we need without having to download them first. Yes, we do process on one platform and then need to visualise or combine with sensitive data on another.”

What are the key tools for our users

We have long established a key set of tools which have been set up on common machines in the form of JASPY²⁰. Scientific Python and Jupyter seem to dominate the community with strong evidence for a lot of bespoke dataset and data analysis tools being created.

“Own code combined with modelling and visualisation packages - Jupyter etc.”

“We write our own code in python and keep in a project GitHub, SNAP for sentinel data”

“Many of the packages made available by the Open-Radar community. I then write my own python code using these packages (stored on Bitbucket) to process our data. I also use Jupyter notebooks for analysis and teaching surrounding WSR.”

Key Software and tools that are not available

One of the main issues around JASMIN has been licensing for proprietary software and the lack of a windows environment. The absent software reported in survey responses were:

“Matlab”, “IDL”, “CDL”, “NCO”, “CDO”

Use of HPC and workflows

The use of HPC outside of JASMIN occurred on a variety of platforms for model runs. The use of Cylc for model workflows was very much in evidence.

²⁰ <https://help.jasmin.ac.uk/docs/software-on-jasmin/jaspy-envs/>

Is the ability to reproduce the scientific analysis/maintaining the ability to process data as important as archiving the dataset?

This is the question which received the strongest positive response. This fits with our experiences archiving data for the NCEO LTSS programme where it was frequently stated that the most important thing to preserve was the process or workflow which generated the data was a very important thing to preserve. The process could be rerun for their own purposes, to improve the process, to extend existing data sets or to generate new data for specific applications. Some examples from survey responses are as follows:

“Yes, we model crop production and water use over large regions and globally, being able to maintain this ability with updated/regional data would be fantastic”

“Reproducibility is important for post-processing historic data and considering improvements to the processing chain.”

“Yes. We do air quality and climate modelling. The emissions/meteorological datasets changes often, so the ability to process is as important as archiving.”

“Yes. The ability to repeat analysis to create a timeseries of outputs is crucial to monitor change”

“Yes - our main role is mapping and time series analyses for the environmental data above.”

Enhance User Survey and Interviews

We are going through a period where many projects are surveying their user communities. To avoid survey fatigue we align with the enhance project who shared their survey results in relation to NERC DataLabs in the form of the enhance project report.

The enhance²¹ project report drew on a recent case study of UKCEH to uncover current and future visions of DRI for environmental science. The study engaged UKCEH environmental scientists, data managers, software, developers, and other staff, in semi-structured interviews, workshops about ‘FAIR’ assets, and a survey. The dataset we are drawing from includes 28 interviews, 81 survey data responses, and 36 workshop participants across 4 workshops. Given the overall size of the dataset, we offer a preliminary and illustrative (rather than representative) analysis of the key issues relating to digital assets in DRI (broadly), as well as DataLabs

²¹ DataLabs and discoverability: a summary report on the DataLabs enhancements project; Green, David Philip ; Lord, Carolynne ; Widdicks, Kelly ; Roebuck, Jennifer; Gouldsbrough, Lily ; Hollaway, Mike ; Blair, Gordon ; <https://nora.nerc.ac.uk/id/eprint/539039/>

(specifically), concerning discoverability. These insights are derived from a deductive read-through (Bingham & Witkowsky 2022), supplemented with a simple search across the data.

Annex A: Key Reports and Topic Strawman Questions

RDA Framework

RDaF V2.0 publication is available at <https://doi.org/10.6028/NIST.SP.1500-18r2>

Framework Foundation – Lifecycle Stages, Topics, and Subtopics

The foundation of the RDaF consists of lifecycle stages, topics, and subtopics selected by the RDaF team using a vast amount of stakeholder input as described in [Section 2](#). The RDaF research data lifecycle graphic depicted in [Fig. 2](#) is cyclical rather than linear and has six stages defined below. Each stage is interconnected to all other stages, i.e., a stage can lead into any other stage. An organization or individual may initially approach the lifecycle from any stage and subsequently address any other stage. It is likely that an organization or individual will be involved in all lifecycle stages simultaneously, though with different levels of intensity or capacity.

Envision – This lifecycle stage encompasses a review of the overall strategies and drivers of an organization’s research data program. In this lifecycle stage, choices and decisions are made that together chart a high-level course of action to achieve desired organizational goals, including how the research data program is incorporated into an organization’s data governance strategy.

Plan – This lifecycle stage encompasses the activities associated with preparing for data acquisition, selection of data formats and storage solutions, and anticipation of data sharing and dissemination strategies and policies, including how a research data program is incorporated into an organization’s data management plan.

Generate/Acquire – This lifecycle stage covers the generation of raw research data, both experimentally and computationally, within an organization or by an individual, and the collection or acquisition of research data produced outside of an organization.

Process/Analyze – This lifecycle stage concerns the actions performed on generated or externally acquired research data to yield processed research data, typically using software, from which observations and conclusions can be made.

Share/Use/Reuse – This lifecycle stage outlines how raw and processed research data are disseminated, used, and reused within an organization or by an individual and any constraints or encouragements to use/reuse such data. This stage also includes the dissemination, use, and reuse of raw and processed research data outside an organization.

Preserve/Discard – This lifecycle stage delineates the end-of-use and end-of-life provisions for research data by an organization or individual and includes records management, archiving, and safe disposal.

Themes to consider:

[4 Overarching Themes](#)

[4.1 Community Engagement](#)

[4.2 Cost Implications and Sustainability](#)

[4.3 Culture](#)

[4.4 Curation and Stewardship](#)

[4.5 Data Quality](#)

[4.6 Data Standards](#)

[4.7 Diversity, Equity, Inclusion, and Accessibility](#)

[4.8 Ethics, Trust, and the CARE Principles](#)

[4.9 Legal Considerations](#)

[4.10 Metadata and Provenance](#)

[4.11 Reproducibility and the FAIR Data Principles](#)

[4.12 Security and Privacy](#)

[4.13 Software Tools](#)

[4.14 Training, Education, and Workforce Development](#)

Fair Principles

<https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

Care Principles

https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5d3799de845604000199cd24/t/6397b363b502ff481fce6baf/1670886246948/CARE%2BPrinciples_One%2BPagers%2BFINAL_Oct_17_2019.pdf

EDS TopicStrawman/Discussion Questions

1. What are your community platforms?
2. Can you provide us with a technical overview of your platform and/or archive and (links to documents, relevant reports or presentations are fine)
 1. Can you provide us with an overview of your data holdings (volume, number of datasets, number of different formats)?
 2. Can you give us a breakdown of different file formats held?
 3. What data access services does your archive provide?
 4. What data analysis services platforms do you provide?
 5. What hosting capabilities do you provide
 6. What group workspaces do you provide and how could you accommodate users from other platforms/communities. What are the current limitations on this?
2. How do you see the role of the analysis platforms in your organization?
3. What is your strategy for service development, and do you have a business model?
4. Do you have any evidence on current/potential impact of data analysis on scientific output?
5. How can this be improved through interoperability of data archives and platforms?
6. What improvements would your users most like to see? Can you point us to any relevant user feedback?
7. Identifying Tools, Notebooks and Services of Interest
 1. What tools, notebooks and services do you create/maintain?
 2. What are the key externally produced software, tools, notebooks and services that your community use? This would include things like software libraries for reading specific file formats.
 3. Are there project outputs in the form of notebooks documentation and tools that should be associated with your data holdings (in the short term at least)?
 4. Are there training tools or notebook that you would like to run on your platforms
8. Discovery of tools and services
 1. How do you make your tools and services discoverable?
 2. Do you hold any metadata for your tools and services?
 3. Are there any discovery services you would like to expose your tools and service to?
9. Structure, workflow, code and documentation standards
 1. Do you recommend any software or documentation standards to your community
 2. Do you enforce any of these standards
10. Technical dependencies and Virtual Environments

1. Do you record any technical dependencies for software/notebooks generated on your systems, so that they can be run in the future or ported to do a different platform
 2. Can users on your platforms identify technical dependencies and what support do you provide for them
 3. How could this be improved?
11. Citation, access to and navigation to data within the archive
1. How do you provide access to your data holding and identify access condition to platform users
 2. How do your users navigate the data structure within your archive
 3. Do you hold 3rd party restructured data
12. Archival, Preservation and Retirement
1. Do you currently preserve, archive or retire software or notebooks?
 2. If yes how do you do this?
13. Open-source software licensing
1. What are licensing recommendations for software and/or notebooks
14. Proprietary Software or highly restricted data on Data Analysis Platform
1. Have you negotiated deploying proprietary software on your archive. If so what was the agreement and could this be done centrally by UKRI?
 2. How did you restrict user access to proprietary software and provide assurance to vendors?
 3. How important is proprietary software for your user community
 4. Do you support restricted access to datasets. If so how did you do it
 5. Do you deal with any other type of restricted material i.e. algorithms or models
15. Publishing, Versioning and DOI's for software and notebooks
1. How do you store and/or publish software/notebooks
 2. How do you version and/or publish software/notebooks
 3. Do you issue DOI's for software/notebooks
16. Data Standards:
1. Does your platform/archive advocate specific data standards
 2. Do you keep any record of tools or libraries to be associated with specific formats or datasets
17. Data Transfer between archives and platforms:
1. What are your main tools for transferring data between platforms and archives – what are their limits and restrictions
18. What do you think the security and privacy issues are around EDS data holdings.
19. Workflows
20. AI and vocabularies
21. AI tools
22. What do you think are the main barriers to platform interoperability?
23. What accommodations do you make for accessibility?

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Annex B: BOOST User Survey questions

EDS Data Analysis Platform User Survey

The purpose of this survey is to:

- Identify platforms that you are currently using to analyse and produce new datasets
 - Understand issues/barriers that you are facing using data from different domains
 - Understand barriers to using different platforms
 - Understand the type and range of analysis you wish to perform
- * Indicates required question

1.

Please provide your name *

2.

Please provide your email address *

3.

What is your affiliation? BGS *

4. What sort of data do you use for your scientific work?

Please indicate information such as dataset name, file format and size, if available.

*

5. What sort of data do you use for your scientific work?

Please indicate information such as dataset name, file format and size, if available.

*

6. What sort of data do you use for your scientific work?

Please indicate information such as dataset name, file format and size, if available.

*

7. Which EDS data centres do you get your data from? (**Check as many as apply**) *

Check all that apply.

British Oceanographic Data Centre

Environmental Information Data Centre

UK Polar Data Centre

Centre for Environmental Data Analysis

National Geoscience Data Centre

None

8.

How do you download/use/access data from EDS data centres?

For example: manual download, programmatic access, http, WGET, SPARQL, direct access to CEDA archive through JASMIN, direct access through Datalabs asset catalogue.

*

9.

Do you get environmental data from any other sources?

Please list the main ones. For example, Google Earth Engine, Kings College University Data, Copernicus, Edina, Met Office, Sensor data directly from instruments, Experiments and Field Surveys held by research groups, Health data held by the NHS, Road traffic information held by local authorities, Ground truth or in-situ data, Training data for AI.

10.

Do you have any data interoperability issues?

Example: Semantics: it is difficult to know if you are comparing the same (like for like)

Example: Data formats: the data from some domains are proprietary or unusable

Example: Scale or projection: the data we need to use is the wrong scale or projection to incorporate with our data

Example: Data is too large and unwieldy: I need to extract the spatial extent data I need from a very large dataset and transfer it to local machine for analysis with other data sets

*

11.

What data analysis platforms do you use, and why?

Examples: JASMIN, NERC Datalabs, Google Colabs, My personal computer running windows, GIS (e.g. ArcGIS, QGIS).

*

12. Do you combine the use of different platforms for different activities?

Example: I use NERC Datalabs to collaborate on a Jupyter Notebook that relies on an unpublished dataset hosted on the platform. This allows us to work on the same version of the code/data, and we do not have to transfer any data.

Example: I use Datalabs to share Jupyter Notebooks of teaching materials that can be shared across the centres.

Example: I create the data using the AI capabilities of Google Collabs, I archive the data at CEDA and then provide post project training using Binder and the OpenDAP service. The Jupyter Notebooks are kept on Zenodo. I analyze spatial data in a GIS to ascertain where to conduct fieldwork and then deposit data collected from field work with the appropriate data centre.

*

13.

Is there anything that would further improve interoperability between data analysis platforms and/or data

providers? If so, what would this enable?

For example: Are there climate models you run on JASMIN that you would also like to run on DAFNI?

Do you have notebooks that you would like to run on different platforms? Do you process on one platform and then need to visualise or combine with sensitive data on another?

14.

What tools do you use to perform your analysis? Please list some key examples.

For example:

SNAP for sentinel data.

We write our own code in python and keep in a project GitHub/Jupyter notebooks.

We use 3D modelling and visualisation packages to visualise our data.

I use Dask through the JupyterLab plug-in, for the parallel processing of my python scripts.

15.

Are some key software/tools not available on the platforms you use?

If yes, please list those that impair your scientific work.

16.

Do you use HPC or workflows for data processing/analysis?

If yes, please provide as much detail as you can.

17.

Is the ability to reproduce the scientific analysis/maintain the ability to process data as important as archiving

the dataset? If yes, could you describe.

For example: We produce biomass maps using AI and sentinel data. We would like to maintain the ability to do this for different regions or using Near Real time in the future.

18.

If yes could you expand on what you like to to maintain or run on another platform?

19.

Are there any other major blockers in your ability to analyze or process data in the way you would like?

20.

Are you happy for us to contact you to follow up on your answers? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

GDPR Statement

At STFC (being a Council under, and part of, United Kingdom Research and Innovation), it is our mission to work with our partners to ensure that world-leading research and innovation continues to grow and flourish in the UK. Integral to this is our commitment to protecting and safeguarding your data privacy. If you are happy for STFC to collect information from this survey on data interoperability and for STFC to hold your data for this purpose, please tick the box below. The data will be downloaded, anonymised, and stored on STFC's secure servers. The data will be used to report to the UK Government and within STFC and UKRI. Our privacy policy can be found at <https://www.ukri.org/privacy-notice>. UKRI and STFC RAL Space comply with the requirements of the GDPR with regards to the collection, storage, processing, and disclosure of personal information and is committed to upholding the GDPR's core data protection principles. A full notice of UKRI's position with regards to Freedom of Information and the General Data Protection Regulations (GDPR) (EU) (2016/679) can be found at <https://www.ukri.org/freedom-of-information>.

21.

Please tick to confirm that you have read and agree to the privacy statement. *

Check all that apply.

I have read the above and understand how my personal data and the data that I provide will be used and processed by UKRI.

Annex C: Cross Domain Questionnaire on Jupyter Notebooks Best Practice

Jupyter Notebooks Best Practice and Software Repository for NERC Domains

https://ceos.org/document_management/Working_Groups/WGISS/Documents/WGISS%20Best%20Practices/CEOS_JupyterNotebooks_Best%20Practice_v1.1.pdf

The above document is the result of the BOOST Jupyter Notebooks case study carried out with the international CEOS community, which assessed the state of art in this and adjacent domains. This is a set of questions intended to ascertain what EDS archives would need for a common Jupyter Notebooks/Software repository ?

Name of Data Centre/Platform (e.g. CEH/NERC Data labs):

Name and contact of people filling in questionnaire:(e.g. Esther Conway)

Q1. Could you give example of the type of notebooks you may want to keep in a common repository. For example, training notebooks, notebooks for processing workflows, notebooks to support data analysis.

Q.2 Other tools – Jupyter Notebooks were initially chosen due their prevalence across domains. However, we expect that there are many other specialist community based and dataset specific tools that would benefit from inclusion in an EDS repository. Note that recommendations such CEOS Service Discovery Best Practice should work with different software and service, not just Jupyter notebooks.

Q3. Technical dependencies – In the technical dependencies section examples are Jupyter notebooks interacting with a data cube, x-array or OpenDAP. Considering the services for your data centre or any other types of technical dependency we should consider.

Q4. Citation section – Would this work for your data holdings?

Q5. Association with data – Could you link a software repository holding to your data catalogues or is this a capability something you would need to develop.

Q6. Preservation – Software is inherently fragile and will have limited lifespan that may be prolonged by good metadata that will allow environment to be reproduced on Data analysis platforms. How long should we reasonably try to maintain notebooks software and how should we differentiate between active and legacy software/tools

Q7. Licensing approach – Would you happy advocating the described approach ?

Q8. Publishing and versioning – Would you be happy for an EDS notebook/software repository to built using Zenodo and Github as described in this section.

Q9. Would you agree with a recommendation for a common Notebooks/Software repository for NERC EDS datacentres that could be used as a test case for national infrastructure. If so, what additional aspects should we consider?